

Multi-Robot Systems: A Brief Technological Review.

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Abstract. Multi-robot systems make it possible to address problems that cannot be solved by a single device, or in a more efficient and robust way. They consist of a set of independent robots, with varying computational, sensing and environmental capabilities, operating in a coordinated manner to achieve a common goal. This coordination generally requires message passing, and thus multi-robot systems can be analyzed as a distributed system. In this article we perform a general review of this type of systems and the state of the art in relation to them.

Keywords: Robotics · Distributed Systems · Multi-Robot Systems

1 Introduction

Robotics is one of the technologies with the greatest presence in the collective imagination, as a result of the extensive thematic treatment that historically has been made in literary and cinematographic works of fiction. Although at the moment far from the expectations created by these works, robots are having a greater and greater impact on our lives, being currently widely used in different industries and services [12].

A *robot* is a device that performs tasks by interacting with the physical world, with a significant degree of autonomy (i.e., it does not act solely by remote operation). To perform these tasks, it is necessary to capture information from the environment and act on it. Any robot must therefore consist of three types of components: sensors (such as a camera, a microphone or a photocell), actuators (such as a wheel or a mechanical arm) and some kind of control mechanism, which activates the latter depending on the input of the former. This control mechanism can be considered as consisting of different *behaviors* that establish relationships between patterns of sensory activation and patterns of action on the environment. The combination of these behaviors, which can be executed sequentially or concurrently, constitutes the program that the robot executes to carry out the given tasks.

It is straightforward to make a robot's control mechanisms capable of solving any computable logic problem. However, robots perform tasks in real environments: changing, unstructured and only partially observable scenarios. In this uncertain setting there are also physical parameters that restrict the ability to act (impossibility of accessing certain locations, travel times, etc.) One of the proposals to address such conditions is the use of a team of robots instead of a single device, which cooperate to achieve a common goal. We speak in this case of multi-robot systems (hereafter MRS), which are expected to be, as a whole, more resilient, adaptable, efficient or faster than a solitary robot. This is a version of multi-agent control applied to physical devices, which in essence is a distributed problem-solving strategy that occurs frequently in nature [31], as is the case with herd, pack or flock behaviors (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Hunting strategy of a wolf pack: (a) approach, (b) attack, (c, d) capture. Cooperative behavior, which is achieved through explicit (sound) and implicit (observation of the behavior of the other members) signals, is much more efficient than individual hunting in this habitat [32]. (Photo credits: Daniel Stahler and Douglas Smith, from [20]).

The most immediate applications of MRSs are those related to logistics, exploration (e.g., mine exploration or space exploration) or large area operations (e.g., surveillance, reconnaissance or hazardous waste cleanup).

2 Physical model

The characteristics of MRS communication are conditioned by diverse factors, both design-related (energy consumption, physical limitations, manufacturing complexity) and circumstantial (physical environment, mobility, availability of frequencies in radio space, accidental disturbances). Communication mechanisms do not necessarily include sophisticated technological means, for example an observable movement can be considered a form of communication (even if the main intention of the mobile robot was not to emit a message - in this case we refer to *implicit communication*). Thus, Dudek's taxonomy [4,5] proposes a classification of MRS that includes the dimensions of range, topology and cost of communication.

- In relation to the range of the communication:
 - COM-NONE: there is no direct communication.
 - COM-NEAR: robots can only communicate with nearby robots.
 - COM-INF : it is possible for a robot to communicate with any other robot.
- In relation to the communication topology:
 - TOP-BROADCAST: it is possible to send a message from one device to all the others.
 - TOP-ADD item: it is possible to communicate with any device knowing its address or name.
 - TOP-TREE item: communication is allowed in a tree hierarchy.
 - TOP-GRAPH item: communication through a network structure is allowed.
- Relative to the cost of communication:
 - BAND-INF: The communication cost can be considered negligible for practical purposes.
 - BAND-MOTION : The communication cost is of a similar order of magnitude to that of moving the robot. This category is characteristic of systems that use the motion itself as a signaling mechanism.
 - BAND-LOW: The communication cost is very high. Systems in this category are expected to consist of virtually independent devices.
 - BAND-ZERO: Communication is not possible.

Many of these properties will depend on spatial characteristics of the system and may therefore be dynamic in nature. In relation to this aspect, Dudek includes a specific dimension to classify systems according to their capacity for spatial organization:

- In relation to the collective reconfiguration capacity:
 - ARR-STATIC: Fixed topology.
 - ARR-COMM: Certain reconfigurations coordinated by the system itself are possible.
 - ARR-DYN: The system topology can be changed arbitrarily.

Dudek's taxonomy makes it possible to understand the diversity of MRSs, conditioned by the large number of different possibilities for communication between mobile elements with varying capacities, constituting heterogeneous groups in dynamic environments.

3 Architectural Model

Under stable and relatively static connectivity conditions, the communications of an MRS could be managed like those of a typical distributed system. However, assuming these characteristics would configure a fragile robotic ensemble, only functional in very restricted missions and scenarios; therefore hybrid architectures are often designed, assuming much more limiting properties. We will consider separately the communication between robots (*Robot to Robot - R2R*) and the communication of the MRS with the control infrastructure (*Robot to Infrastructure - R2I*).

3.1 R2R Architecture

Robot behavior can be managed from a single point of control or be decentralized. In either case, inter-robot communication is usually designed on a *peer to peer* fashion [16]. The obvious advantages are scalability and robustness due to the absence of a single point of failure. If the control is decentralized, the main challenge is to keep the actions of the robots synchronized.

At the physical and data link level, short- and medium-range technologies, such as Bluetooth or Wi-Fi protocols, are often used. At the network level, techniques that make it possible to deploy *ad-hoc* mobile networks are frequent [22], with more or less sophisticated routing schemes where the devices themselves act as dynamic routers. A unique feature of this type of protocol is reactive routing, where the paths between the communication source and destination are computed on demand using a discovery algorithm [17]. Other possibilities include geographic location-based routing [19] and hierarchical protocols [30]. These techniques allow adapting the communication to the MRS situation, enabling the sending of point-to-point messages in changing scenarios such as those described above, where the possible routes may vary dynamically depending on the physical configuration of the group of robots and the environment.

3.2 R2I Architecture

Although coordinated operation of the individual robots occurs through internal message passing to the MRS, the ensemble must typically exchange information with external systems, such as a remote control center or the Internet [10]. Here the physical and link level protocols are more far-reaching, such as WiMAX, 3G/4G/5G mobile networks or satellite communications. Typically, communication with the outside world takes place through a *gateway* that provides the long-range connectivity, which can be one or more of the MRS members themselves. A key consideration in MRS design is the power consumption of long-range communications, since this affects the autonomy of the group. Therefore, it is often necessary to provide greater electrical capacity to the units acting as gateways. This introduces a higher degree of heterogeneity in the MRS (Figure 2). We refer in this case to client-server architectures, in which the client role can be played by individual robots or by the whole, depending on the logical organization of the service. Therefore, the system could also be described in terms of logical levels, for example the operational level, the communications level and the control level.

Fig. 2. MRSs with R2R peer-to-peer communication and individual robots acting as gateways for R2I communication (Source [16])

3.3 Transport protocols

In relation to the transport layer, both in R2R and R2I communication, and in addition to protocols such as TCP or UDP, the relatively frequent use of SCPT (*Stream Control Transmission Protocol*) [14] stands out. SCPT has some useful features for its application to MRSs, such as the capability of multihoming with path control, which allows devices to be simultaneously configured in several networks, maintaining connectivity in case of possible failures. SCPT's multistream capabilities also make it suitable for audio and video retransmission, which is useful for monitoring or teleoperation of robotic systems.

4 Fundamental Model

Since an MRS can be viewed as a typical distributed system, the interaction, failure and safety models are subject to the usual considerations and interpretations, giving rise to specific requirements and characteristics depending on the purpose of the system. We highlight below some of these characteristics that are particularly relevant in the field of robotics.

From the point of view of interaction models, a common requirement for MRSs is the ability to respond in real time to the environment. Whether these responses depend on a centralized control or a distributed behavior scheme, the system design is required to be at least partially synchronous. It is sometimes possible to have an *autonomous nervous system* that responds individually to immediate needs with real-time requirements and relaxes synchronism, bandwidth and latency constraints on the distributed system.

In relation to the failure and security models, it is important to note that the results of an error or system compromise are amplified in an MRS; to the possible consequences considered in a conventional computer system is added the danger of acting, in a potentially damaging way, on the physical world. The design of these systems is usually based on the principle of fault tolerance and considers different independent protection mechanisms.

With regard to cyber-physical security, which includes defense against both an attack on communications or software and versus attempts at physical manipulation of the devices, it is worth mentioning that this is a specific area of research [8] that faces major challenges, such as the multitude of subsystems involved in an MRS, the usual lack of control in the physical space where the system operates, and the variability in the layout of the whole.

5 Middleware

As with any distributed application, development by directly accessing transport layer functions is neither efficient nor desirable from a software engineering point of view. R2R and R2I communications, as well as the coordination of operations and the provision of distributed services (processing, storage, sensing) can be provided in an abstract software layer (*middleware*), which avoids low-level programming and hides most of the heterogeneity of the system, both in relation to the characteristics of the devices, as well as that inherent to the dynamic context of each robot. Due to the youth and complexity of this area of development, existing middleware solutions are integrated into frameworks with disparate, often experimental, capabilities.

- *ROS (Robot Operating System)* [24] is a framework for the development of robotic systems. It is a software infrastructure based on a peer-to-peer topology that allows the execution of independent modules (programmed in any language) to configure the system as a whole. The MRS is represented by a set of nodes that exchange messages under a publisher-subscriber paradigm. Additionally, ROS includes tools providing diverse functionalities for monitoring, software deployment, collaborative development, etc.
- *Player/Stage* [7]: *Player* is a modular middleware oriented to centralized control of MRSs. It is a socket server, which allows the development of client applications in any language that supports sockets. The core functions are separated from the transport functions, so it is possible to use *Player* with different protocols. On the other hand, *Stage* is a simulator that allows the development of MRS applications without the need for physical devices.
- *Orca* [21] is a framework for the development of distributed robotic applications based on *ICE* (Internet Communication Engine). *ICE* is an object-oriented middleware that provides remote execution, grid computing and publisher-subscriber services.
- *MIRA* [6] is a middleware aimed at developing fully distributed robotic applications with peer-to-peer communication. *MIRA* employs a remote object approach that allows modeling anything from sensors to complete robots.
- *Microsoft Robotics Developer Studio (MRDS)* [15] is an application development toolkit for robots based on REST services.

Other alternatives are *ASEBA*, *RT-Middleware*, *OPRoS*, *WURDE*, *RoboComp*, *Urbi*, *MARIE*, *OpenRDK*, *OROCOS*, *SmartSoft* o *CLARAty*. A fairly exhaustive comparison of many of them can be found at [28].

6 Common distributed robotics problems

In order to better understand the possible application of (and the challenges to be faced by) the proposed set of technologies, we describe below some examples of problems that are considered typical in the field of MRSs, in the sense that they are applicable to a very broad set of situations. Solving these problems usually requires a combination of many techniques, such as distributed systems coordination (synchronization, mutual exclusion, leader selection, etc.), multi-agent planning or heuristic optimization.

6.1 Search-coverage

The search-coverage problem consists of efficiently applying a sensor or actuator to all points in a large space. Practical applications include mapping (Figure 3), surface cleaning, object search (such as land mines), surveillance, etc.

The main challenges of such problems are that the geometry of the space to be covered need not be known in advance¹, the efficient organization of MRS to avoid redundancy, how to foresee possible collisions between robots, and so on. The theoretical problem of optimal search-coverage by a single robot can be solved efficiently, however, the multi-robot version is intractable [25], and therefore a multitude of heuristic approaches have been developed dependent on the specific characteristics of the problem [1].

Fig. 3. Examples of collaborative exploration of an MRS with 4 members in two scenarios and with different starting positions (marked with red circles). (Source [3])

6.2 Motion planning and formation control

Motion planning allows each robot to reach a specific position, in the most efficient way possible, without colliding with obstacles in the environment or with the other MRS members.

¹ In this case, we refer to *exploration* problems [2]. For example, NASA's *Cooperative Autonomous Distributed Distributed Robotic Exploration (CADRE)* project raises the use of MRS for the exploration of planets and satellites.

A particular version is the *rendezvous* problem, which occurs when the destination point is coincident (or very close) for all robots.

Currently, the most efficient motion planning systems employ a decentralized approach: initially, each robot plans its path independently, and a distributed algorithm tries to minimize a global cost function by searching a *coordination diagram*, which represents the possible collisions as a function of the system evolution [9].

The problems of formation control add to the need to maintain a certain structure of relative positions as the group moves. Formations may be necessary as an intermediate step to solve another problem or simply to maintain certain features of the SMC, such as line-of-sight between members or communications range. The problem of maintaining the formation is complex if we consider the need for each individual to position himself in relation to the others and the possible obstacles or changes in the geometry of the physical space as the formation progresses. A specific sub-problem is that of recovering the formation once it has been broken, due to intended or accidental reasons. As in the case of motion planning, distributed control algorithms have performed best in general applications [26].

There are also techniques to simulate some collective behaviors present in nature, such as herd or swarm behaviors, which could fall into this category, although they do not try to maintain a given structure but certain properties of the moving set of robots [29].

6.3 Multi-robot tracking

Tracking problems arise from the need to track (e.g., keep in the field of view) different moving targets cooperatively, with possibly less robots than targets. The problem is highly dependent on the specific application characteristics and its resolution is part of an active area of research [27].

6.4 Task distribution

Task distribution refers to the need for an MRS to individually distribute the actions necessary to achieve its goals in an optimal way, considering the capabilities, internal states and positions of each robot, as well as the conditions of the environment at any given time. The problem is central to the development of MRS applications, and has been addressed by different approaches, such as a fair division problem solved by auctions [11], a constrained assignment problem [23] or a version of the multiple traveler problem (mTSP) [13]. Of all these options there are versions with different levels of decentralized execution [18].

7 Closing Remarks

It can be interpreted that an MRS is a robotic system built on top of a distributed system or that the MRS itself is a distributed system. In either case, it is easy to identify a paradigmatic example of the classical concept of a distributed system. Its characteristics can be analyzed from the perspective of logical processes cooperating through message passing, but the physical dimension adds a layer of complexity that poses numerous challenges. Thus, the coordination of multi-robot systems represents a major scientific-technical problem, the applications of which will play a fundamental role in future robotic applications.

References

1. Almadhoun, R., Taha, T., Seneviratne, L., Zweiri, Y.: A survey on multi-robot coverage path planning for model reconstruction and mapping. *SN Applied Sciences* **1**(8), 1–24 (2019)
2. Burgard, W., Moors, M., Stachniss, C., Schneider, F.E.: Coordinated multi-robot exploration. *IEEE Transactions on robotics* **21**(3), 376–386 (2005)
3. Dong, S., Xu, K., Zhou, Q., Tagliasacchi, A., Xin, S., Nießner, M., Chen, B.: Multi-robot collaborative dense scene reconstruction. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)* **38**(4), 1–16 (2019)
4. Dudek, G., Jenkin, M., Milios, E., Wilkes, D.: Organizational characteristics for multi-agent robotic systems
5. Dudek, G., Jenkin, M., Milios, E., Wilkes, D.: A taxonomy for swarm robots. In: *Proceedings of 1993 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS'93)*. vol. 1, pp. 441–447. IEEE (1993)
6. Einhorn, E., Langner, T., Stricker, R., Martin, C., Gross, H.M.: Mira-middleware for robotic applications. In: *2012 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. pp. 2591–2598. IEEE (2012)
7. Gerkey, B., Vaughan, R.T., Howard, A.: The player/stage project: Tools for multi-robot and distributed sensor systems. In: *Proceedings of the 11th international conference on advanced robotics*. vol. 1, pp. 317–323. Citeseer (2003)
8. Gray, R.S., Kotz, D., Cybenko, G., Rus, D.: D’agents: Security in a multiple-language, mobile-agent system. In: *Mobile agents and security*, pp. 154–187. Springer (1998)
9. Guo, Y., Parker, L.E.: A distributed and optimal motion planning approach for multiple mobile robots. In: *Proceedings 2002 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (Cat. No. 02CH37292)*. vol. 3, pp. 2612–2619. IEEE (2002)
10. Guo, Y., Parker, L.E., Madhavan, R.: Towards collaborative robots for infrastructure security applications. In: *Proceedings of International Symposium on Collaborative Technologies and Systems*. vol. 2004, pp. 235–240. Citeseer (2004)
11. Higuera, J.C.G., Dudek, G.: Fair subdivision of multi-robot tasks. In: *2013 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. pp. 3014–3019. IEEE (2013)
12. Hockstein, N.G., Gourin, C., Faust, R., Terris, D.J.: A history of robots: from science fiction to surgical robotics. *Journal of robotic surgery* **1**(2), 113–118 (2007)
13. Hussein, A., Khamis, A.: Market-based approach to multi-robot task allocation. In: *2013 International Conference on Individual and Collective Behaviors in Robotics (ICBR)*. pp. 69–74. IEEE (2013)
14. IETF Network Working Group: Stream control transmission protocol. Rfc, IETF (2000), <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2960>
15. Jackson, J.: Microsoft robotics studio: A technical introduction. *IEEE robotics & automation magazine* **14**(4), 82–87 (2007)
16. Jawhar, I., Mohamed, N., Wu, J., Al-Jaroodi, J.: Networking of multi-robot systems: Architectures and requirements. *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks* **7**(4), 52 (2018)
17. Jonsson, U., Alriksson, F., Larsson, T., Johansson, P., Maguire, G.Q.: Mipmanet-mobile ip for mobile ad hoc networks. In: *2000 First Annual Workshop on Mobile and Ad Hoc Networking and Computing. MobiHOC (Cat. No. 00EX444)*. pp. 75–85. IEEE (2000)
18. Khamis, A., Hussein, A., Elmogy, A.: Multi-robot task allocation: A review of the state-of-the-art. *Cooperative Robots and Sensor Networks 2015* pp. 31–51 (2015)
19. Ko, Y.B., Vaidya, N.H.: Location-aided routing (lar) in mobile ad hoc networks. *Wireless networks* **6**(4), 307–321 (2000)
20. MacNulty, D.R., Tallian, A., Stahler, D.R., Smith, D.W.: Influence of group size on the success of wolves hunting bison. *PloS one* **9**(11), e112884 (2014)

21. Makarenko, A., Brooks, A., Kaupp, T.: Orca: Components for robotics. In: International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS). pp. 163–168. Citeseer (2006)
22. de Morais Cordeiro, C., Agrawal, D.P.: Ad hoc and sensor networks: theory and applications. World Scientific (2011)
23. Nam, C., Shell, D.A.: Assignment algorithms for modeling resource contention and interference in multi-robot task-allocation. In: 2014 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA). pp. 2158–2163. IEEE (2014)
24. Quigley, M., Conley, K., Gerkey, B., Faust, J., Foote, T., Leibs, J., Wheeler, R., Ng, A.Y., et al.: Ros: an open-source robot operating system. In: ICRA workshop on open source software. vol. 3, p. 5. Kobe, Japan (2009)
25. Rekleitis, I., New, A.P., Rankin, E.S., Choset, H.: Efficient boustrophedon multi-robot coverage: an algorithmic approach. *Annals of Mathematics and Artificial Intelligence* **52**(2), 109–142 (2008)
26. Ren, W., Sorensen, N.: Distributed coordination architecture for multi-robot formation control. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **56**(4), 324–333 (2008)
27. Robin, C., Lacroix, S.: Multi-robot target detection and tracking: taxonomy and survey. *Autonomous Robots* **40**(4), 729–760 (2016)
28. Sahni, Y., Cao, J., Jiang, S.: Middleware for multi-robot systems. In: Mission-Oriented Sensor Networks and Systems: Art and Science, pp. 633–673. Springer (2019)
29. Shi, Z., Tu, J., Zhang, Q., Liu, L., Wei, J.: A survey of swarm robotics system. In: International Conference in Swarm Intelligence. pp. 564–572. Springer (2012)
30. Singh, S.P., Sharma, S.: A survey on cluster based routing protocols in wireless sensor networks. *Procedia computer science* **45**, 687–695 (2015)
31. Steinberg, M.: Biologically-inspired approaches for self-organization, adaptation, and collaboration of heterogeneous autonomous systems. In: Defense Transformation and Net-Centric Systems 2011. vol. 8062, p. 80620H. International Society for Optics and Photonics (2011)
32. Wahde, M.: Introduction to autonomous robots. Lecture Notes from the course Autonomous Agents, Chalmers university of technology (2012)